

Straw, lime, and manganese dioxide amendments for iron-toxic rice soils

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A nutritional disorder of lowland rice associated with excess water-soluble Fe often occurs on strongly acid soils. It has been identified in the Philippines, Vietnam, Thailand, Malaysia, India, Sri Lanka, Liberia, Senegal, Colombia, and China. Lime and MnO_2 alleviate the disorder.

In the greenhouse, we evaluated the effect of straw (0 and 0.25%), $CaCO_3$ (0 and 0.25%), and MnO_2 (0 and 0.005%), in a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ factorial, randomized complete block design in 4 replications on the growth and yield of IR26 in an iron-toxic acid soil. NPK was added to soil collected from the top 20 cm of a Sulfaquept from Malinao, Albay, Philippines. The soil had pH 3.4, 0.64% organic C, 0.049% total N, 2.4% active Fe, 1.3 mmol/kg exchangeable K, and 4.4 mg/kg available P (Olsen). Four 20-d-old IR26 seedlings were transplanted in each pot 2 wk after submergence. The soil solution was analyzed fortnightly.

Although 4 wk after transplanting (WAT), Fe concentrations in the soil

1. Influence of straw, $CaCO_3$, and MnO_2 on the kinetics of water-soluble Fe^{2+} in a submerged iron-toxic soil, IRRI.

2. Grain and straw yields as affected by different additive treatments, IRRI.

3. Fe content of shoots at 4 WAT and straw at harvest as affected by different additive treatments, IRRI.

solution differed mainly in the lime factor (Fig. 1), Fe toxicity symptoms were severe in untreated soil, moderately severe in straw-treated soil, mild in MnO_2 -treated soil, and virtually absent in all lime treatments. Eight wk after transplanting, plants on straw-treated soil began to recover, which may be associa-

ted with declining Fe concentration in the soil solution.

Lime alone or combined with MnO_2 produced the highest straw and grain yields (Fig. 2). The benefits of lime were associated with lower concentrations of Fe in the soil solution and in rice shoots (4 WAT) and mature straw (Fig. 3). Straw and MnO_2 alone or combined gave moderate yield increases which were associated with a lower Fe content of the shoots (4 WAT) than in the untreated plants.

As an inexpensive amendment for iron-toxic soils, straw merits further study. We need to ascertain

1. if smaller amounts of N, P, and $CaCO_3$ are sufficient, when combined with the straw, to prevent N and P deficiency and Fe toxicity in early stages of rice growth;
2. how long the residual effects of straw, lime, and MnO_2 incorporation will last; and
3. what is the optimum amount of straw and timing of transplanting. □

Effect of soil moisture and seeding depth on seedling emergence of two rices

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We evaluated the effect of soil moisture content and seeding depth on seedling emergence of Safri 17 and IR36. Seeds were planted in a loam soil in the laboratory at 1, 2, 3, and 5 cm deep and water was applied 1, 2, or 3 cm deep.

The figure gives percent seedling emergence as influenced by depth of water application based on isolines of percent emergence. When IR36 was planted 5 cm deep, seedling emergence was low. Percent emergence for Safri 17 was similar at seeding depths of 1 and 5 cm.

Soil moisture level corresponding to soil water potential between -0.5 to -2.0 bars was most favorable for seedling

emergence, followed by the range – 1.5 to 2.0 bars.

Safri 17 germination at all depths and soil moisture levels was better than that of IR36.

Although farmers who direct seed their fields usually plant seeds deeper than normal to have good seedling emergence at the onset of the monsoon, our results show that increasing the planting depth of rice varieties sensitive to seed placement depth can adversely affect seedling emergence. Therefore, appropriate seeding depth for the variety to be planted should be practiced. □

Emergence dynamics of Safri 17 and IR36 as influenced by depth of water application and seeding depth.

Response of rice to zinc and sulfur

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Zn and S deficiencies are major constraints to irrigated rice in the Joyertek (Joydebpur) boro project area of Bangladesh. We evaluated Zn and S deficiency in a farmer field at Joyertek in 1983 boro with IR8 as the test variety. Soil was sandy loam with pH 7.6, 30 ppm available S (Ca-P extractable), and 0.6 ppm available Zn (0.05 NHC1 extractable). All plots received the recommended 60-9-17 kg NPK/ha. ZnSO₄ and zinc oxysulfate at 10 kg/ha were applied to Zn-treated plots. For S, 200 kg gypsum/ha

was applied. Both were broadcast and incorporated 4 wk after transplanting, when nutrient deficiencies were visible. Symptoms were brown spots and rusty streaks on the leaves, very poor growth, and light yellowing. Plants were harvested 7 wk after treatment. Chemical analysis and dry matter yield are in the table.

Applying gypsum and Zn in two forms dramatically increased the dry matter yield of IR8 as compared with the control. Deficiency symptoms disappeared in Zn-treated plots 2-3 wk after treatment. ZnSO₄ performed better than zinc oxysulfate. Plant analysis for Zn (1N HCl extraction) showed that plant Zn concentration in treated plots was still below the critical level, although it was relatively higher than in the control plots. Although

S concentration (nitric-perchloric acid digestion) and N:S were satisfactory, applying gypsum also improved rice growth. □

Effect of N, P, and K on available P and K in sodic soil

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We evaluated the effect of N, P, and K on available P and K in soil and on rice and wheat yields in a long-term field experiment on a partially reclaimed sodic soil at Karnal.

The soil was naturally highly sodic, but 3 yr (1971-74) of cropping and gypsum amendments had reduced pH to 9.2 and exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) to 32.0 in the 0.15 cm surface layer of soil. Soil was 24% clay, 24% silt, and 52% sand, with 8.8 meq cation exchange capacity/100 g, 2.75% CaCO₃, 225 kg available N/ha, 0.25% organic carbon, 15.0 ppm available P, and 160 ppm K.

The 1974-82 experiment had eight treatments (Table 1) and was in a ran-

Effect of Zn and S on the performance of IR8 at Joyertek, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Dry matter yield (g/m ²)	Total Zn (ppm)	Total S (%)	Total N (%)	N:S
Control	63	16	.250	1.96	7.8
ZnSO ₄	554	25	.159	1.30	8.2
Zinc oxysulfate	112	19	.237	1.98	8.4
Gypsum	163	18	.219	1.58	7.2